

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the tenth regular issue of 2024. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research papers and the editorial board and our guest reviewers for their extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions and the generous support of the consortium members enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality. I would also like to thank our broader community for reading and incorporating sound J.UCS papers into their research.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce six accepted papers involving 17 authors from six different countries (Argentina, Brazil, Ecuador, Hong Kong, India, Saudi Arabia).

Álex dos Santos Moura, Fábio Gomes Rocha, and Michel S. Soares from Brazil propose in their research a recommendation tool based on information retrieval to assist developers in choosing the suitable microservices pattern to solve a given problem. In a collaborative research effort between Ecuador and Argentina, Gonzalo P. Espinel-Mena, José L. Carrillo-Medina, Eddie E. Galarza, and Mario Matias Urbieto discuss a systematic mapping of configuration management activities in software product line. Edward Kai Fung Dang, Robert Wing Pong Luk, and Qing Li from Hong Kong contribute to the forum for negative results with their study on word bigrams for pseudo-relevance feedback in information retrieval. Prateek Thakral and Yugal Kumar from India present in their work an improved water flow optimizer (IWFO) algorithm for cluster analysis that can address the issues of traditional and heuristic algorithms. Samit Bhanja, Banani Ghose, and Abhishek Das from India highlight their findings on multi-step-ahead time series forecasting using a deep learning and fuzzy time series-based error correction method. And last but not least, Abdullilah A. Alotaibi and Salman A. AlQahtani from Saudi Arabia present in their research an intelligent distributed channel selection framework with hybrid mode selection for interference mitigation in D2D based 5G networks.

Enjoy Reading!

Best regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at